

SCF CI Calculation on Organic Sulphur Compounds : Part I. Thiophene, Thiazole, 1, 2, 5- and 1, 3, 4-Thiadiazole

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In order to establish the electronic configuration of the sulphur atom in five membered organic sulphur compounds, SCF-CI calculations have been made on thiophene, thiazole, 1, 2, 5- and 1, 3, 4-thiadiazole, assuming the sulphur atom to be in $s^2p_xp_y p_z^2$ electronic configuration and donating two p_z electrons to the π -electron system of these molecules. The calculated and available experimental spectral data were found to be in excellent agreement.

Since Longuet-Higgins¹ made Huckel MO calculations on thiophene using $3p-3d$ hybrid atomic orbitals on sulphur, various workers^{2,3} have reported the result of HMO and SCF MO calculations on the π -electron system of heterocyclic organic molecules containing sulphur. A controversy still exists as to whether d -orbital participation should be included in the MO calculations on these molecules or the original suggestion of Wheland and Pauling⁴, that sulphur contributes only $3p$ AO to the π -electron MO, is a better description of such systems.

Recent microwave spectroscopic, electron and X-ray diffraction data on five membered heterocyclic organic compounds^{9,10,11,12} containing sulphur and sulphur and nitrogen atoms shows that in all these compounds the bond angle at the sulphur atom is close to 90° , indicating that the σ -bonds are formed from p_x and p_y orbitals of sulphur. Moreover, even under drastic conditions, these compounds cannot be quaternised at the sulphur center, which evidently means that the lone pair electrons on sulphur have no directional character. This can happen if these lone pair electrons have purely s -character. Consequently the experimental data suggest that the electronic structure of the sulphur atom in five membered organic sulphur compound is $s^2p_xp_y p_z^2$ in which the two p_z -electrons enter into conjugation with the π -electron system of the rest of the molecule. Purely theoretical considerations

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also indicate very little *d*-contribution in the bonding of the sulphur atom in these compounds, at least in thiophene. If free atom Slater exponents are used for sulphur and carbon atomic orbitals then the carbon $2p_z$ -sulphur $3p_z$ overlap integral comes out to be 0.492, while the carbon $2p_z$ sulphur $3d_{xz, yz}$ overlap is only 0.109¹⁴. The overlap criterion therefore indicates that inclusion of *d*-hybridization will not lead to any increase in bond strength of the carbon-sulphur bond.

The object of the present investigation was to make SCF-CI calculations on thiophene, thiazole, 1, 2, 5- and 1, 3, 4 thiadiazole molecules. Because of the above arguments it has been assumed that sulphur contributes only $3p_z$ -electrons to the π -electron system of these molecules. It may be mentioned that SCF calculations have been reported on these systems^{5,7,8}, but no configurational interaction (CI) was introduced by any of the previous authors. Incidentally, Sappenfield and Kreevoy⁶ have reported LACO CI calculations on thiophene in which they arrived at the amazing conclusion that, in order to get good agreement with experimental values, the ionization energy of sulphur must be taken as an empirical parameter. In addition, in all previous calculations the authors had to assume some form for the carbon, nitrogen and sulphur atomic orbitals in order to estimate the bicentric integrals since the authors were not in agreement as to whether the free atom AO's or deformed AO's should be used in molecular calculations, different ones have used different atomic orbital exponents, which introduced additional empirical factors in the calculations. The only approximation which does not take into account the exact form of the AO in the calculation of bicentric integrals is due to Mataga¹⁷. This approximation has been found to work very well for carbon and nitrogen system, but the usefulness of this approximation for compound containing sulphur has not been explored. With this end in view we have included thiophene in our calculation since for this molecule detailed spectral data are available and exhaustive SCF calculations have been reported.

Method of calculation : The theoretical principles involved in SCF-CI calculation have been discussed in greater detail by various authors^{15,16}. The numerical computation uses the fact that the first order density matrix $\frac{1}{2}P_{\mu\nu}$ is idempotent and that the total energy is a minimum for correct $P_{\mu\nu}$. An initial $P_{\mu\nu}$ based on the corresponding Hückel type matrix was brought closer to satisfying the equations for correct $P_{\mu\nu}$. Then introducing the electron repulsion integrals iteration procedure was carried out. About nine iterations were necessary for self consistency to within 0.0001 ev.

After self-consistency is obtained for the ground state energy, (configurational) wave functions for the excited configurations were constructed from the virtual orbitals. If we denote by ${}^1\chi_{i \rightarrow k}$ the singlet configurational wave function in which one electron is excited from an occupied orbital ψ_i to virtual orbital ψ_k , and the corresponding triplet

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wave function by ${}^3\chi_{i \rightarrow k}$, then the excitation energy corresponding the transition $i \rightarrow k$ may be expressed as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} E({}^1\chi_{i \rightarrow k}) &= ({}^1\chi_{i \rightarrow k} | H | {}^1\chi_{i \rightarrow k}) - (\chi_0 | H | \chi_0) \\ &= E_k - E_i - (ik | G | ik) + 2(ik | G | ki) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} E({}^3\chi_{i \rightarrow k}) &= ({}^3\chi_{i \rightarrow k} | H | {}^3\chi_{i \rightarrow k}) - (\chi_0 | H | \chi_0) \\ &= E_k - E_i - (ik | G | ik) \end{aligned}$$

where $(pq|G/rs) = \int \psi_p^*(1)\psi_q^*(2) \frac{e^2}{r_{12}} \psi_r(1)\psi_s(2) d\tau_1 d\tau_2$

and the E_k 's are SCF orbital energies.

The interconfigurational matrix elements were obtained in a similar way

$$\begin{aligned} ({}^1\chi_{i \rightarrow k} | H | {}^1\chi_{i \rightarrow l}) &= -(jk | G | il) + 2(jk | G | li) \\ ({}^3\chi_{i \rightarrow k} | H | {}^3\chi_{i \rightarrow l}) &= -(jk | G | il) \end{aligned}$$

An excited state wave function was approximated by a linear combination of singly excited configurational function $\chi_{i \rightarrow k}$.

Selection of Parameters : In this calculation it has been assumed that sulphur contributes two while nitrogen and carbon contributes one p_z -electron to the π -electron system of the whole molecule. The core Hamiltonian and one center electron interaction integrals were calculated by methods due to Pariser and Parr¹⁵ and the bicentric integrals were calculated by Mataga¹⁷ approximation. For these calculations the valence state ionization energy and electron affinities were required. These were calculated by a method due to Skinner and Pritchard¹³ from the atomic spectral data of C.E. Moore. The only arbitrary parameter involved the core resonance integrals. The values used in this calculation are given in Table I.

TABLE I

MO parameters used in the calculation

$I_N = 14.63$ ev.	$I_S = 12.50$ ev.	$I_C = 11.54$ ev.
$E_N = 2.36$	$E_S = 2.70$	$E_C = 0.46$
$\beta_{CC}^C = -2.39$	$\beta_{CS}^C = -2.14$	$\beta_{CN}^C = -2.57$
		$\beta_{NS}^C = -2.0$

The molecular geometries are shown in the Fig. 1. Since the experimental data on thiophene and thiazole were incomplete, and idealised geometry has been assumed.

Fig. 1. Molecular Geometry.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The SCF eigen values and eigenvectors are given in Table II.

TABLE II

SCF eigenvalues and eigenvectors

	Energy levels (ev.)	SCF vectors				
		C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	C_5
Thiophene	-15.0762	0.8069	0.3537	0.2222	0.2222	0.3537
	-11.3065	-0.4890	0.1890	0.5871	0.5871	0.1890
	-9.6563	0	0.6018	0.3712	-0.3712	-0.6018
	-1.0841	0.3314	-0.5824	0.3255	0.3255	-0.5824
	+0.9317	0	-0.3712	0.6018	-0.6018	0.3712
Thiazole	-15.4105	0.7605	0.3278	0.2468	0.3290	0.3806
	-12.2728	-0.5459	0.0006	0.4219	0.6893	0.2206
	-9.8731	0.0936	-0.6498	-0.5090	0.2231	0.5099
	-1.2931	-0.3373	0.5162	-0.2053	-0.3566	0.6709
	+0.6734	0.0308	-0.4512	0.6780	-0.4893	0.3101
1,2,4-Thiadiazole	-15.8292	0.6803	0.3572	0.3754	0.3754	0.3572
	-12.9972	-0.6477	0.0534	0.5360	0.5360	0.0534
	-10.4840	0	0.5686	0.4202	-0.4202	-0.5686
	-1.3880	0.3428	-0.6078	0.2677	0.2677	-0.6078
	+0.3421	0	-0.4202	0.5686	-0.5686	0.4202
1,2,5-thiadiazole	-15.8729	0.6936	0.4310	0.2712	0.2712	0.4310
	-11.6173	-0.6155	0.1590	0.5340	0.5340	0.1590
	-11.6149	0	0.6308	0.3194	-0.3194	-0.6308
	-2.0895	0.3741	-0.5374	0.3756	0.3756	-0.5374
	+0.3923	0	-0.3194	0.6308	-0.6308	-0.3194

In Table III we give the computed spectral transition energies for thiophene. Experimentally known levels are also listed.

TABLE III

Spectral transition energies in thiophene (in eV)

Sym.	Calc.	Exp. ⁵
¹ A ₁	9.28	—
¹ B ₁	7.84	—
³ A ₁	5.88	—
³ B ₁	5.63	5.63
¹ A ₁	4.69	5.16
¹ B ₁	5.41	5.33
³ B ₁	3.83	3.90—3.96
³ A ₁	2.33	—

It may be observed that the agreement is as good if not better than the results obtained by previous authors, particularly Bielefeld and Fitts⁵ who have taken into account *3d* and *4p* states in addition to *3p* orbitals of sulphur. Pryce⁵ has reported some short wave bands near 7.2 eV, but they have not been unequivocally assigned to any π -electron transition of thiophene. These experimental value for this band is therefore not recorded in Table III, although we do find one such π -electron transition in our calculation. We may therefore conclude that use of the Mataga approximation is reasonably well justified for organic sulphur compounds.

In the Table IV we summarise the calculated and experimental transition energies in thiazole, 1, 2, 5- and 1, 3, 4- thiadiazole.

TABLE IV

Experimental and calculated transition energies (in eV)

	Thiazole		1,2,5 Thiadiazole		1,3,4-Thiadiazole	
	Calc.	Exp. ⁹	Calc.	Exp. ⁹	Calc.	Exp.
Singlet	6.56	—	¹ A ₁ 7.81	—	¹ A ₁ 6.21	—
	5.00	5.27	¹ A ₁ 5.47	—	¹ B ₁ 4.87	—
Triplet	—	—	¹ B ₁ 5.03	4.86	—	—
	3.89	—	³ A ₁ 3.65	—	³ A ₁ 4.01	—
	2.37	—	³ B ₁ 2.90	—	³ B ₁ 2.72	—

For these systems, however, experimental data are incomplete and only a few peaks have been recorded. Nevertheless, the calculated value reproduces these few spectral data reasonably well.

We may conclude that $s^2p_xp_y p_z^2$ is a good description of the electronic state of the sulphur atom in five membered heterocyclic organic compounds.